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Editorial

NICAEA@1700: Call for Reconciliation

Credo in unum Deum... With these words begins the momentous profession of faith, the core symbol of our faith. The first ecumenical council, held in Nicaea – an ancient city located within the modern Turkish city of İznik – in 325, played a very crucial role in the formulation of this statement of our faith. According to CCC 195, “*The Niceno-Constantinopolitan or Nicene Creed* draws its great authority from the fact that it stems from the first two ecumenical Councils (in 325 and 381). It remains common to all the great Churches of both East and West to this day.” As the Jubilee Year 2025, which began on 24 December 2024, concludes with the closing of the Holy Doors of St. Peter’s Basilica on 6 January 2026, the Catholic Church also concludes the yearlong reflection on Nicaea, which took place side by side with the Jubilee Year.

Vidyajyoti Journal of Theological Reflection (VJTR) rarely comes up with thematic issues. The last thematic issue of VJTR was published in March 2022, which also turned out to be the last edited issue of my predecessor, late Fr. Poulouse Mangai SJ. That special issue was brought out on the occasion of the celebration of the Ignatian Year (20 May

2021 – 31 July 2022), having the theme: “To see all things new in Christ.” With great joy, the editorial board of VJTR dedicates this special issue to the Ecumenical Council of Nicaea.

1. TWO RECENT VATICAN DOCUMENTS ON THE COUNCIL OF NICAEA

What is the dogmatic and existential relevance of the Council of Nicaea for our world and the universal Church today? This question is concretely answered in two important Vatican documents. On 16 December 2024, International Theological Commission (ITC) published a scholarly theological document titled: “Jesus Christ, Son of God, Saviour” (JCSGS) to commemorate the 1700th anniversary of the Ecumenical Council of Nicaea (325-2025). On 23 November 2025, on the Solemnity of Christ the King, Pope Leo XIV promulgated an Apostolic Letter titled *In Unitate Fidei* (IUF). ITC’s JCSGS throws light on the dogmatic relevance of the Council for our times, and Pope Leo’s IUF focuses more on practical aspects. VJTR editorial board strongly recommends our readers to read, reflect, meditate, and draw inspiration from these important documents, readily available on the Vatican’s Website: vatican.va.

Pope Leo wrote the apostolic letter in order “to encourage the whole Church to renew her enthusiasm for the profession of faith” (IUF 1). We can never overestimate the significance of the first ecumenical council at Nicaea. According to the ITC document, “The Council of Nicaea is particularly revered by the Eastern Churches, not simply as one Council among many or the first in a series, but as *the* Council par excellence, which promulgated the confession of faith of the ‘318 Orthodox Fathers’” (JCSGS 43). Along with the two documents mentioned above, four papers in this special issue help us to understand the importance and implications of this Council, and be enthused about the Nicene Creed.

2. FOUR INSIGHTFUL PAPERS IN THIS ISSUE

What is the dogmatic and existential relevance of the Council of Nicaea for India and the Indian Church today? This question is answered in the four papers of this special issue.

2.1 Indispensability of the Nicene Dogma

The first paper, titled “Council of Nicaea: The Indian Critique of Christian Dogma,” written by Dr. Enrico Beltramini, an American Scholar, throws light on the significance and indispensability of the Nicene Dogma, in the face of Indian Theologians’ “soft” and “hard” versions of critique of Dogmas couched in Greek philosophy. The notion of “Two Powers in Heaven” – having Canaanite origin and adapted in rabbinic literature – possibly playing a role in the formulation of the *homooúsios* in the Nicene Creed is especially interesting. The key argument of the author can be summarized in the following quote from Pope Leo’s Apostolic Letter:

In order to express the truth of the faith, the Council adopted two words – “substance” (*ousia*) and “consubstantial” (*homooúsios*) – which are not found in Scripture. The Council’s intention in doing so was not to replace biblical statements with Greek philosophy. On the contrary, the Council used these terms precisely to affirm biblical faith with clarity and to distinguish it from Arius’ error, which was deeply influenced by Hellenism (IUF 5).

2.2 Influence of the Nicene Thinking on Asian Christian Faith

The second paper, titled “The Influence of Nicene Thinking for Christian Faith from an Asian/Indian Perspective,” by Dr. P. R. John, the former Principal of Vidyajyoti, systematically traces the resonances of the Nicene Creed on Asian/Indian Theology. The author considers De Nobili’s concept of Christ as *Satguru*, Upadhyay’s *Saccidananda*, and Soares-

Prabhu's *dharma* along the lines of Nicene thinking. After providing key inculturated notions of major Asian/Indian theologians from the 15th century, 18th and 19th centuries, and the 20th century, the author dwells on the key notion of "light from light." This, according to him, is "a hermeneutic key to understand the influence of Nicene thinking in Asia." ITC document also affirms this position, when it states: "the Eastern tradition emphasises the understanding of Christ as 'light from light'" (JCSJS 17). Pope Leo also dedicates a full paragraph for this important phrase in the Creed (cf. IUF 6).

2.3 Beyond the *Homoousios* and the Scandal of Incarnation

The third paper, titled "The Incarnate Revolution: God's Hierarchy-Shattering Flesh and the Anathema of Religious Power," by Fr. Midhun J Francis Kochukallanvila SJ, focuses on the aspect of Incarnation. Going beyond the dogmatic formulation, the author pushes for the practical implication of the Creed, which reveals itself in the enfleshment of the Divine Logos. In fact, as per the ITC document, there is no dichotomy between dogmatic formulation and practical implication because "*homoousios* itself helps us to realise the unheard-of nature of the kenosis of the Incarnation" (JCSJS 27; cf. IUF 7). According to the author, this kenosis of the Incarnation manifests a consecrated anthropology and commissions us to see Christ in the distressing disguise of the poor and humbly encounter him in all cultures.

2.4 Nicene Creed and Christian Unity

Pope Leo states that the Council of Nicaea is relevant today because of its great ecumenical value" (IUF 12). The fourth paper, titled "Nicene Creed and Christian Unity: Creed, Laity, and Synodality as a Path of Communion," by Dr. Soroj Mullick SDB, throws light on the ecumenical and synodal significance of the Council. The author discovers in the Nicene Creed foundation for unity and lay participation. He encourages the readers to move from Creed

to commitment and confession to communion by overcoming "ecclesial eczema: the pathology of disunity within." On 28 November 2025, during the ecumenical prayer service, near the archaeological excavations of the ancient Basilica of Saint Neophytos, Pope Leo appealed to the Christians, "The more we are reconciled, the more we Christians can bear credible witness to the Gospel of Jesus Christ, which is a proclamation of hope for all."

CONCLUSION

The genius of the Council of Nicaea lies in its expression of the Christian faith in the language and culture of its time. It is our duty and responsibility to make faith intelligible to the people of our time and place. Uprooted and borrowed faith is barren; faith has to be rooted and grounded in our soil so that it can bear much fruit. Let us not look at dogmas and creeds as alien to us, but try to make sense of them and make them rooted and grounded in our culture and ethos! The 1700th anniversary of the Nicene Creed is beckoning us to bear witness to Christian unity and make our Christian faith dialogue with the culture, language, and people of our times.

Keywords: Council of Nicaea, Nicene Creed, *In Unitate Fidei*, *Jesus Christ, Son of God, Saviour*, Pope Leo XIV.

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